

Capacitor Degradation Monitoring for LLC Resonant Converter based on Discharging Profile

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Project Description and Objectives

Hybrid Electric regional Aircraft distribution Technologies (HECATE) aims to deliver transformative technologies to electrical distribution for future Hybrid Electric Aircraft. Task is given to evaluate the PHM for LVDC power converter and life cycle assessment.

The Multi-layer Ceramic (MLC) capacitor is a critical yet vulnerable component in power electronic converters, where degradation leads to a decrease in capacitance. Monitoring capacitance is crucial for predicting the lifespan of MLC capacitors.

This paper introduces a **monitoring scheme** specifically for LLC resonant converters that estimates the capacitance of its capacitor on the output side.

Methodology

A. Condition monitoring

	Al-Caps	MPPF-Caps	MLC-Caps
EOL criteria	$C/C_0 < 80\%$	$C/C_0 < 95\%$	$C/C_0 < 90\%$

B. Calculation model

$$V_{cap} = V_{dc} e^{-\frac{t}{(R_{ESR} + R_L)C}}$$

C. Flowchat representation

The discharging profile-based capacitance estimation method is utilized by observing the capacitor voltage over time.

A deviation from the expected discharge profile suggests alterations in the capacitor physical condition.

Results

ESR (mΩ)	Capacitors (μF)	Loads (Ω)	Estimated C	
			Value (μF)	Error (%)
100	220	4	220.6	1.20
		8	221.4	0.63
		16	220.6	0.39
100	100	4	100.5	1.36
		8	100.7	0.77
		16	100.4	0.51

Results under different capacitance and load values.

